

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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ISSUES OF REFLECTION OF FINANCIAL RESULTS IN REPORTS AND IMPROVEMENT OF AUDIT

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Abstract: The article discusses the problems associated with the formation of financial results when preparing financial statements, in accordance with national and international financial reporting standards, as well as analytical techniques for auditing financial results, which will lead to increased efficiency, developed recommendations for assessing the profitability of companies. The influence of financial reporting principles on the formation of financial results is revealed.

Key words: financial results, income, expenses, profit, marginal income (profit), direct cost, discontinuation of operations, events after the reporting date, changes in financial statements, deviations in estimates.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada milliy va xalqaro standartlar asosida tuzilgan moliyaviy hisobotlarda aniqlangan moliyaviy natijalarni aks ettirilishi bilan bog’liq ayrim muammolar hamda moliyaviy natijalar auditi bo’yicha kompaniyalarning samaradorlik ko’rsatkichlarini oshirishga yo’naltirilgan tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqish imkonini oshiradigan va analitik jarayonida qo’llaniladigan usullari ko’rib chiqilgan. Moliyaviy hisobotlarni tuzishda foydalanadigan tamoyillarning moliyaviy natijalarni shakllanishiga ta’siri ochib berilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: moliyaviy natijalar, daromadlar, xarajatlar, foyda, marjinal daromad (foyda), direkt-kost, faoliyat to’xtatilishi, hisobot sanasidan so’ngi hodisalar, moliyaviy hisobotdagi o’zgarishlar, baholashdagi og’ishlar.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются проблемы, связанные с формированием финансовых результатов при составлении финансовой отчётности, в соответствии с национальными и международными стандартами финансовой отчётности, а также аналитические приёмы при аудите финансовых результатов, которые приведут к повышению эффективности, разрабатываемых рекомендации по оценке прибыльности компаний. Раскрывается влияние принципов финансовой отчётности на формирование финансового результата.

Ключевые слова: финансовые результаты, доходы, расходы, прибыль, маржинальный доход (прибыль), директ-кост, прекращение деятельности, события после отчётной даты, изменения в финансовой отчётности, отклонения в оценках.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of financial statements is to provide information on the financial situation of the enterprise, its activities and the movement of its funds, which is necessary for a wide group of users to make economic decisions. Because, financial reporting is the result of the structural unification of economic relations into groups in terms of nature and essence. The final stage of the process of generalization and classification is the provision of very short information, which is divided into categories. Financial statements also indicate the capabilities of the enterprise, the results of the implementation of management.

Profit is an important quality indicator of each enterprise. Problems such as predicting internal and external factors that affect the financial stability of enterprises, creating an informative and theoretical basis for making effective management decisions on their promising development require the organization of accounting and auditing using modern methods in reflecting the results of the activities of enterprises.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The issues of accounting and auditing of material results have been studied by many scientists and covered in the literature, for example Sheremet A.D. [5], Remizova Ye.Yu. [3], Poshersnik N.V. [2], Hendriksen E.S. [4], Karimov A.A. [1] et al. In our opinion, the Russian economist scientist N. The definition of posherstnik comprehensively and simply covered this concept: “indicators of financial results represent the economic effect obtained as a result of the activities of the enterprise” [6].

A. Avlokulov believes: «an important aspect of the formation of a report on financial results is the amount of indicators designed to meet the needs of users, which is reflected in it. The increase in the amount of these

indicators gives users more information, while revealing the conditions for their occurrence. A decrease in the amount of indicators will be convenient for them to read, but will not fully reveal the conditions for the formation of benefits and losses, giving less information" [6].

RESEARCH METHODS

This article uses the rules of analysis and synthesis, scientific abstraction, unualization and methods of comparative interpretation. The scientific basis of the article is the formation of the algorithm for compiling a report on financial results and the implementation of its audit by comparing research data conducted by scientists in domestic and foreign publications.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The requirements for which the most attention is paid according to modern requirements are the transparency of information and its acceptability for all. For this reason, the structure of the report on financial results is based on the classification of income and expenses by type of activity. In the formation of reporting indicators on financial results in all developed countries, an approach was used precisely by types of activities. But the main issue in the formation of the report is the size of the indicators presented. That is, according to accounting standards, in the report on financial results, it is necessary to reveal the following: net income from the sale of products; gross financial result; other operating income and expenses from the main activity; financial results of the main economic activity (profit or loss); other income and expenses related to financial activity; financial result of the general.

However, certain aspects of the enterprise's activities were not considered. For instance, based on accounting standards and the guidelines for preparing financial statements, the outcomes of suspended activities are typically reported as part of the income and losses from general (ordinary) business operations. Events distinctly different from the regular activities of the enterprise or those that do not occur as part of such activities are excluded from income and losses. In such instances, income or losses arising from the cessation of activities may be categorized as extraordinary items.

Each of the suspended operations is revealed in the explanations (draw 1).

Draw 1. Annotations that are reflected in explanations on suspended operations [3].

The second, important point of attention should be paid to the condition, which is when drawing up a” report on financial results « account changes in assessments (drawing 2).

Draw 2. Changes in assessment that make changes to the Financial Performance Report [4].

In the following cases, the results of changes in Account Estimates are included in the determination of net income and losses:

- | | |
|--|--|
| • to determine net income and loss in the reporting period (if these changes only affected this period); | • to the report of the period in which the changes occurred and to the subsequent reporting periods in which these changes affected. |
|--|--|

To ensure comparability of financial statements across periods where account estimates are revised, such adjustments should be reflected in the classification items of the financial results report, using the same criteria as those previously applied. The nature and impact of changes in account estimates that significantly influence the results of the current period or are likely to lead to notable changes in subsequent periods—must be disclosed. If the effects of these changes cannot be quantified, the lack of such determination should also be disclosed.

It is crucial to recognize that significant errors may occur when completing Form 2 of financial statements. Serious errors are those identified in the current period that are significant enough to render financial statements of previous periods unreliable. Corrections of such errors should be adjusted against the net income or loss of the current reporting period.

Adjustments for significant errors from prior periods should be reflected by altering the undistributed profit balance at the beginning of the year. Additionally, corresponding data from prior periods should be restated. If errors are of an unacceptable magnitude, such information may be excluded from subsequent reports. When correcting prior period errors through adjustments to net income or loss in the current period, comparative data for previous years should be appropriately restated. However, supplementary information should be presented in a separate column to detail the adjustments to net income or loss from the current or prior periods where such significant errors were corrected.

In some cases, amendments to financial reports may occur even after their initial preparation. Changes in accounting policies are permissible only when explicitly authorized or if they enhance the accuracy and reliability of the financial statements. The financial impact of accounting policy changes should be recorded by adjusting the opening balance of unallocated profits on the balance sheet and incorporating these adjustments into the determination of net income or loss for the reporting period.

The business entity must simultaneously reveal the following information during the introduction of the amendment:

1) the essence of an important mistake;

2) the amount of change recognized as income or loss in the current period;

3) additional information is the amount of changes regarding each period provided, as well as the amount of changes related to the periods included in additional information regarding the periods before that period. If in practice it is not used to cite additional information, then the reasons for this should be revealed.

Draw 3. Information that is obliged to be revealed at the time of making an amendment to the data of the business entity [3].

If changes in accounting policies have a significant impact on the reporting period in relation to the previous period of presentation of financial statements, or affect the future reporting periods, the business entity should reveal the following information in the explanations:

- 1) causes of amendments;
- 2) the amount of Corrections in the reporting period and previous periods provided;
- 3) the amount of Correction taken into account in the net income or loss of the current period;
- 4) the amount of Corrections made to comparative data regarding the periods before the reporting period;
- 5) additional information is provided the amount of Corrections made to each reporting period, the amount of Corrections associated with the periods before the periods included in the financial statements. This situation should also be revealed if comparative information is included or additional information cannot be provided;
- 6) recalculated comparative data or the reasons why it is not advisable to recalculate them.

So, to summarize, some disadvantages can be seen when filling out a report on financial results. In our opinion, at least four indicators should be brought in the report on profits and losses arising from the current requirements:

- 1) gross profit,
- 2) profit from other treatments,
- 3) profit before tax exclusion,
- 4) Net Profit after tax payment.

In addition:

- size of realization,
- realized product cost,
- income from interest receipts and investments,
- information such as profits and losses incurred on foreign currency transactions must also be taken into account.

The law "On accounting" and the standards of accounting are understood mainly by income, which is derived from the ordinary activities of the economic entity, including income from the realization of the product (work performed, service provided), interest received, dividends, royalties, etc. Some discrepancies also arise between the schet plan in practice and the requirements of the tax system, which are used when accounting for financial results.

Fourth, as you know, according to the regulation "on the structure of costs for the production and sale of products (work, services) and the procedure for the formation of financial results", the types of activities of economic entities cannot be fully reflected in terms of the occurrence of income and expenses.

When drawing up a report on financial results, first of all, the purpose of accounting standards is also to highlight the articles of reporting on financial results by economic entities on the basis of general principles and to classify, supplement and present them. In our country, some problems have been identified in bringing accounting standards closer to the process of international standards, therefore, in our opinion, it is necessary to develop a new form of reporting on financial results, which meets the requirements of the interests of domestic and foreign users of the report and accounting principles.

The final indicator of the report on moliative results is net profit. Profit is an important quality indicator of each enterprise. According to the regulation "on the composition of the costs of production and sale of products (works, services) and the procedure for the formation of financial results « approved by the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 54 of February 15, 1999, the profit of enterprises is determined by the following indicators: gross profit from the sale of products; ; profit received until tax is paid; net profit of the year.

Profit, in turn, is an important object not only of accounting and reporting, but also of audit. The Auditor checks that the profit is calculated correctly according to the concluded contract, used under the requirements of the law during the year. The Auditor checks the correct calculation of the profit indicator through the following operations:

- operations by types of income;
- operations by type of cost;
- profit transactions used throughout the year.

The suitability of these transactions for tax connoisseurs is studied in depth by the auditor. For this, information on financial results is widely used. To check the correctness of the tax paid from the profit of the enterprise, the auditor draws up a special schedule.

In the Audit process, as a standard practice, indicators for financial results (income, expenses, profit) are checked by comparison with the data "balance sheet of accounting" (Form 1), "Report on financial results" (Form 2), "report on cash flows" (Form 4), "Report on private equity" (form 5). The Auditor checks the data in these documents by comparing them with the current data of accounting. The profit of the enterprise represents the

efficient use of resources as important quality indicators. For this reason, it is possible to know the profitability of assets, depending on the profit received.

In the Audit process, the opportunity is created to develop reasonable recommendations aimed at further increasing profits if the level of profitability by types of assets is analyzed.

The fact that large enterprises in the current period provide molyav reports on the basis of both national and international standards makes it necessary to evaluate the activities of enterprises through indicators used in international practice. One such indicator is the marginal profit of the enterprise. In the process of auditing financial results, it is important to identify and evaluate this indicator.

Variable costs are removed from gross income to determine the marginal profit of the enterprise. The output represents marginal benefit. And after the removal of fixed costs from this indicator, the profit at the disposal of the enterprise remains. The principle of marginal benefit lies in the "direct-costing" method of cost accounting, which is widely used in basic international practice. The advantage of this method is that when checking costs and financial results, the auditor will be able to develop reasonable recommendations aimed at reducing variable costs, as well as increasing marginal profits, in receipts from product realization. The results of the audit of the profit indicator are reflected in the audit report and conclusion.

After conducting an audit of international practice, the auditor can give the client under investigation a different type of conclusion to the enterprise. A satisfactory auditor's conclusion may involve a number of problems. The Auditor in such a conclusion indicates that the information in the financial statements meets the requirement, the benefits and losses indicated in it, the movement of funds meets the requirements in the law and regulatory documents on current accounting:

- financial reporting is based on accurate, transparent and reliable objective accounting information;
- the accounting policy at the enterprise is correctly selected, accounting is in accordance with the requirements imposed on it;
- tax obligations are timely, fully calculated;
- the explanations written to the financial statements are correct;
- domestic control is confirmed by the reliability of economic transactions and their effectiveness;
- it should be indicated that the information in the financial statements does not contradict the information of the auditor about the enterprise.

It is known that according to the Audit Standard and audit summary standards, the answers to the following questions should be found before making a conclusion:

- is the conclusion illuminated in compliance with accounting rules in the conclusion of financial statements completed at the enterprise?
- has the sequence seen in the previous report been followed during the reporting period?
- does the summary contain opinions and considerations that are not required in the financial report?

Thus, the auditor's conclusion is divided into conclusions that are a summary or explanatory note without explanation. The experience of developed countries shows that 90% of the conclusions correspond to the conclusions of the auditor, in which the explanation is not written. Of course, the following five rules should be observed in such conclusions:

1. All necessary reporting forms should include reports on the balance sheet, financial results. Statements about the benefit to the fund and, finally, the movement of funds must be included in the financial statement.
2. When writing its conclusion, the Auditor is obliged to adhere to three basic rules: specialization, independence, professional ethics.
3. The Auditor's conclusion should contain three templates about the object (planned, internal economic audit, possession of sufficient information).
4. Financial statements in general must comply with the rules of financial statements;
5. Not all contracts should reveal the secret of Commerce (the opinions on which explanatory letters are required are provided).

The audit summary is an official legal document for all legal entities and individuals, state authorities and governing bodies, local self-government bodies, judicial and investigative bodies. The final part of the audit report, issued on the results of the mandatory audit of accounting, is an integral part of the report in question and has legal force.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It can be concluded from the above:

1. Some discrepancies also arise between the schet plan in practice and the requirements of the tax system, which are used when accounting for financial results. In order to take into account the completion of the financial results of the enterprise, we propose to open schets on the profit or loss received from each activity

in the final financial results scheme. The results on these schets are summarized at the end of the reporting month.

2. The results of suspended activities according to accounting standards and the rules for filling out financial statements are usually included in the income and damage of the general (ordinary) activities of the farm. In such cases, the income or loss from the suspension of activity can also be classified as an emergency substance, which, in turn, also results in some imbalances between the requirements of the tax system, for this reason it is necessary to revise the issue.

3. Today, the presentation of molar reports at most enterprises on the basis of both national and international standards assumes the assessment of the activities of enterprises through indicators used in international practice. One such indicator is the marginal profit of the enterprise. In the process of auditing financial results, it is important to identify and evaluate this indicator.

4. The report, compiled under international standards, shows an indicator of marginal profit instead of gross profit, which is reflected on financial results. The advantage of this method is that when checking costs and financial results, the auditor will be able to develop reasonable recommendations aimed at reducing variable costs, as well as increasing marginal profits, in receipts from product realization.

So, all summarizing, it can be said that if in accounting the reporting period follows tomoyils on conceptual grounds in the reflection of income and expenses, that is, their compliance with the principles of compliance and Reserve, leads to an improvement in the accounting of financial results and an increase in transparency, accuracy.

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